

MICROWAVE-ASSISTED EXTRACTION OF PHENOLIC FROM CACAO POD HUSKS - AN ALTERNATIVE FOR VALORISATION

Shinta Rosalia Dewi^{1 2*}, Lee Stevens¹, Derek Irvine¹, Rebecca Ferrari¹, Eleanor Binner¹

¹Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, University of Nottingham, NG7 2RD, Nottingham, United Kingdom

²Department of Bioprocess Engineering, Universitas Brawijaya, 65145, Malang, Indonesia

*shinta.dewi@nottingham.ac.uk

Keywords: Microwave, Bio-mass applications, Biomass/Waste, cacao pod husks, phenolic

Abstract

As a primary waste by-product (ca. 70-75% of total weight of cacao fruit), ten tonnes of wet cacao pod husks (CPH) are discarded to produce a tonne of dry cacao beans [1]. Although a major environmental issue in the cacao industry, CPH contains phenolic compounds that have garnered much interest due to their antioxidant activities and resulting beneficial health properties. Therefore, this study has investigated valorisation of CPH by comparing the extraction of phenolic compounds using microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) with conventional solvent extraction (CSE). Extraction time, temperature, ethanol concentration, and solvent to feed (S/F) ratio were investigated to obtain the maximum yield. The extract quality was presented as total phenolic content (TPC) which was measured by using a UV/Vis Spectrophotometer. The results showed that 50% ethanol was the most appropriate solvent for extracting total phenolics from CPH. This was attributed to the solubility, with both MAE and CSE requiring the same extraction time and solvent consumption. However, at a lower temperature (60 °C), MAE could produce higher TPC (107.3 ± 1.4 mg GAE/g dw) than CSE at 70 °C (105.4 ± 0.9 mg GAE/g dw) even when the same heating rate was applied. It can be believed that the high extraction yield on MAE is due to the selective heating effect. Results of this study suggest that MAE has potential to valorise CPH waste into valuable ingredients based on phenolic compounds. A future research study is proposed to investigate the potential of CPH extract as an antioxidant and food colourant.

1. Introduction

Theobroma cacao, known as food of Gods, is one of the most important tropical plants that produce various products of chocolate and its derivatives. In the cacao industry, fresh cacao beans are processed into products whilst cacao pod husks (CPH) are generally discarded as waste. Indonesia generates over four thousand tonnes of CPH yearly, creating waste and environmental problems. However, CPH contains valuable phenolic compounds which have many health benefits. The primary phenolic compounds found in CPH are gallic acid, catechin, (-)-epicatechin, quercetin, p-coumaric acid and photocatechuic acid which are promising as natural antioxidants and could be used as ingredients in functional foods [2]. The phenolic compounds in pods were reported with a value of 150.9 mg gallic acid equivalent of phenolic per gram dry CPH, which had antioxidant potential of 97.6% radical scavenging. This value has proved to delay lipid oxidation in palm olein during storage [3]. Therefore, the recovery of phenolic compounds from CPH is one way to valorise CPH into more valuable products while reducing the amount of bio-waste produced during cacao production.

The most common extraction methods to extract phenolic compounds from plants or biomass are maceration, Soxhlet, reflux or other conventional solvent extraction (CSE) methods. Because of their low cost and ease of use, those conventional methods are widely used. However, they were revealed to have environmental issues and were inefficient due to the huge amounts of organic solvent required and time [4]. Therefore, several novel extraction methods, such as supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) [5], ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) [6], [7] and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) [6], [8]–[10] have been developed to overcome these limitations. By using supercritical fluids as the extracting solvent, SFE could produce higher phenolic yield with lower solvent and time consumptions compared with CSE [5]. UAE has also been reported to have twice higher yield than that of CSE in faster extraction time on potato peels extraction [7]. While Huma et al [6] investigated the phenolic extraction from carob kibble using MAE, UAE and CSE and reported that the high extraction yield obtained by MAE in 4.5 min were comparable to those from UAE and CSE for 30 and 120 min, respectively. MAE offers the main benefits of volumetric and selective heating effect, leading an increase in phenolic yield. Volumetric heating allows the electromagnetic energy to be transferred directly inside the system resulted in rapid heating [11], so it can significantly reduce the processing time. This direct interaction between the mixture system and microwave energy leads in the quick release of target compounds from plant matrix into the surrounding solvent [12]. On the other hand, the direct comparison of MAE and CSE studied by Galan et al [8] proved that the extraction of phenolic from sea buckthorn leaves was selectively heated above 50 °C offering an increased yield at and above 60 °C.

Based on those studies, it is clear that MAE can provide a high extraction yield in a shorter extraction time. Therefore, this work examined the phenolic extraction from CPH by using MAE and compared with CSE. The objectives of this study are to (1) compare the MAE and CSE using the same bulk heating rate to understand the advantages of MAE over CSE, (2) maximise the total phenolic content (TPC) yield of CPH extract under several extraction parameters: extraction time and temperature, solvent concentration, and solvent to feed (S/F) ratio.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Materials

Cacao was harvested from Malang, Indonesia. The cacao pod husk (CPH) was cut, sliced into small size (\pm 2-4 cm) and dried in a forced-air dryer at 50 °C to a final moisture content of 9.25%. The dehydrated CPH chips were ground into powder and sieved through a 38-micron screen to get CPH with uniform particle size distribution. CPH powder (\leq 38-micron) was brown in colour and was stored at room temperature until use.

2.2 Microwave-assisted extraction

Phenolic extraction from CPH was carried out using a Miniflow 200SS (Sairem) batch reactor at 2.45 kHz and 120 W power. CPH powder (\pm 1 g) was extracted using ethanol/water mixture in a Pyrex reactor (inner dia. 39 mL, height 70 mm) which was then covered with a rubber stopper. The bulk temperature inside the reactor was monitored and controlled using a temperature optical fibre at the desired temperature. An external magnetic stirrer (IKA magnetic stirrer) was placed at the bottom of the microwave reactor to stir the sample mixture and set it at 1200 rpm. The effect of extraction time and temperature, various ethanol/water concentrations, and solvent to feed (S/F) ratio were investigated. Details of experimental conditions can be seen in Table 1. The extract was then separated using centrifuge. All extractions and their total phenolic content (TPC) analysis were carried out in triplicate.

2.3 Reference procedure: Conventional solvent extraction (CSE)

CSE experiments were designed to replicate the MAE conditions. It was processed at the same parameter treatments (extraction time and temperature, solvent concentration, S/F

ratio) as shown in Table 1. To achieve the same heating rate as MAE, the sample was immersed in 120 °C ethylene glycol bath (EgB) until reached the set temperature before being transferred to a water bath (WB). This method was found to achieve a very similar bulk heating profile to the MAE experiment, as shown in Fig 1B. Each mixture of CPH and solvent was stirred at 1200 rpm, and the temperature of the sample inside the reactor was measured using an alcohol thermometer. The extract was then separated using a centrifuge. All extractions and their total phenolic content (TPC) analysis were carried out in triplicate.

Table 1. Experimental conditions for phenolic extraction

Extraction parameter	Extraction method	Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)
Extraction time and temperature	MAE	50%(v/v) aqueous-ethanol	50, 60, 70 °C	1, 5, 10, 15, 30
	CSE	S/F ratio of 40:1 mL/g		
Ethanol concentration	MAE	Deionised water, 10, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 90, and	60 °C	5
	CSE	100%ethanol/water S/F ratio of 40:1 mL/g	70 °C	
Solvent to feed (S/F) ratio	MAE	50%(v/v) aqueous-ethanol S/F ratio of 20:1; 30:1;	60 °C	5
	CSE	35:1; 40:1; 50:1 mL/g	70 °C	

2.4 Quantification of total phenolic content (TPC) of CPH extract

TPC of CPH extracts was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method based on Galan et al [8] procedure. CPH extract (0.5 mL) was mixed with 0.5 mL Folin-Ciocalteu 1N (Sigma-Aldrich) and 7.5 mL deionised water and stirred for 3 min. Thereafter, 1.5 mL of Na₂CO₃ 20%(w/v) (Sigma-Aldrich) was added to the mixture and incubated for 1h. The mixture absorbance was read at 760 nm using a UV/Vis Spectrophotometer (Cecil CE1020S, United Kingdom). A blank solution was made by changing the extract with deionised water. A standard curve was set up using gallic acid standard (Sigma-Aldrich) ranging from 0 to 200 mg/L. The TPC is expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalent per gram dry weight of sample (mg GAE/g dw).

2.5 Dielectric properties measurements

Dielectric properties were measured using an Agilent 85070E Dielectric Probe Kit. The experimental setup consisted of a high performance probe equipped with an electronic calibration (Ecal) module. The performance probe was connected to an Agilent N5232A PNA-L (Purpose Network Analyser) operating at 500 kHz-10 GHz via a high-quality coaxial cable. To measure the dielectric properties of the solvent, 40 mL of each solvent was placed in 100 mL beaker. To measure the dielectric properties of mixture of CPH and solvent, CPH powder (1 g) was placed in 100 mL beaker and added by 40 mL solvent. Each mixture was then heated at a temperature range of 20-70 °C and the dielectric properties were measured immediately after taking the sample out of heating by immersing the probe in the test solvent.

3. Results and Discussion

During microwave heating, absorbed power and bulk temperature profile were measured (Fig 1A). From the graph in Fig. 1A, the set temperature (60 °C) was reached for 75s, (heating phase). Energy absorbed by the system during heating phase and holding phase were 8.97 and 1.15 kJ, respectively, totalling 10.12 kJ. Temperature measured during the process is bulk temperature; the specific temperature of plant material or solvent could be hotter or cooler than bulk temperature, depending on their dielectric properties [8].

Fig. 1. Comparison of MAE and CSE experiments at 60 °C set-point temperature, 5 min extraction time, 50% (v/v) ethanol (40:1 v/w), stirring rate 1200 rpm: (A) Absorbed power and temperature profiles for MAE experiments; (B) Bulk temperature profile for MAE and CSE

3.1 Effect of extraction time and temperature

The extraction yields are dependent on temperature and extraction time, so investigating the extraction time and temperature is critical to maximising extraction of TPC as well as prevent the degradation of phenolic compounds. Firstly, the combination of extraction temperature of 50, 60 and 70 °C and extraction time of 1, 5, 10, 15, and 30 min were investigated, and the results were shown in Fig. 2. The TPC values ranged from 86.01 to 107.32 mg GAE/g dw which the maximum yields on both MAE and CSE were obtained at 5 min extraction time. This finding (Fig. 2) indicated that the best time for extracting phenolic from CPH was 5 min, and the TPC yields tended to decrease when the extraction time was extended up to 30 min. This might be because of the degradation of extracted phenolic by longer exposure to heating. On the other hand, the effect of extraction temperature on MAE and CSE showed a different trend. The TPC obtained by CSE increased by the increase of temperature, while on MAE, the TPC yield increased from 50 to 60 °C then decreased at 70 °C. The decrease in TPC yield at 70 °C presumably due to the degradation of extracted phenolic at a higher temperature. Volf et al. [13] stated that natural phenolics from grape seed such as gallic acid, experienced thermal degradation when heated at temperature of 60, 80 and 100 °C. The degradation rate of gallic acid presented 12% and 20% of degradation rate at 60 and 100 °C, respectively.

Fig. 2. Effect of extraction time and temperature on TPC yields (CPH with particle size $\leq 38\mu\text{m}$, 50% (v/v) ethanol (40/1 v/w), stirring rate 1200 rpm): (A) extraction temperature of 50 °C; (B) extraction temperature of 60 °C; (C) extraction temperature of 70 °C, mean \pm S.D. (n=9, triplicate extraction and triplicate analysis)

In general, comparing both methods at 5 min extraction time, MAE showed 5% higher TPC value than CSE at 60 °C, even both have the same heating rate. It indicates that a higher TPC on MAE may be attributed to a selective heating effect. This finding is supported by Galan et al [8] who found that MAE produced 8% higher TPC yield instead of CSE due to the selective heating effect. They suggested that MAE offered an increased yield at and above 60 °C in the extraction of sea buckthorn leaves. Therefore, according to the maximum TPC yields, further MAE experiments were conducted at 60 °C while CSE at 70 °C for 5 min extraction time. The performance of both methods were then compared at their maximum conditions.

3.2 Effect of ethanol concentration

The selection of extraction solvent depends on the solubility of the target compound in the solvent. Particularly in MAE, the dielectric properties of solvents are an important point, as different solvents exhibit different dielectric properties and therefore different heating rates. Solvent with high dielectric loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) have a high capacity to absorb and dissipate microwave energy into heat [14]. Solvent selection for MAE should therefore consider both dielectric properties and solubility/polarity. In this research, ethanol/water mixtures were used as extraction solvents because they are polar solvents dissolving phenolic compounds and good microwave absorbers. The loss tangent of those various solvents can be seen in Fig. 3B. Comparing the MAE at 60 °C and CSE at 70 °C results (Fig. 3A), it can be seen both methods have similar trends and closed yields. According to Fig. 3A, the TPC contents for both methods increased rapidly and reaching maximum extraction at 50% ethanol before reducing with increasing ethanol percentage. It is clear that CSE could produce the same yield as MAE but required a higher temperatures. The experimental result was in accordance with the previous study reported by Gharekhani et al [12] and Galan et al [8] that the maximum ethanol concentration for phenolic extraction from plant materials was 50% ethanol. Chew et al [15] also showed that binary-solvent of ethanol and water was more useful and favourable than mono-solvent system (deionised water or absolute ethanol) in the extraction of phenolic compounds from *Orthosiphon stamineus* extracts.

Fig. 3. (A) Effect of ethanol concentration on TPC yields (CPH with particle size ≤ 38 -micron, 5 min extraction time, S/F ratio 40:1 v/w, stirring rate 1200 rpm, temperature 60 °C for MAE and 70 °C for CSE), mean \pm S.D. (n=9, triplicate extraction and triplicate analysis); (B) Loss tangent of extraction solvents at 60 °C and 2.45 kHz

Based on Fig. 3B, increasing ethanol percentage increases the loss tangent of both solvent and solvent-CPH mixture. Theoretically, a solvent with a high loss tangent is a suitable solvent for MAE because they are good microwave absorbers. However, the experimental results (Fig. 3A) presented that the TPC decreased above 50%(v/v) ethanol

solvents. There was no correlation between dielectric loss tangent and extraction yield. Moreover, the trend of TPC yields on MAE was the same as CSE. Hence, it is clear that the solubility of phenolic compounds in solvents might be more affected by solvent properties than dielectric properties. The general principle in solvent extraction is “like dissolve like”, which is substances with similar chemical characteristics will dissolve in each other. The results proved that 50%(v/v) ethanol is the most extracted solvent for total phenolics, which means that phenolic compounds have similar properties to 50%(v/v) ethanol than others, and therefore, 50%(v/v) ethanol was chosen as the best extraction solvent for subsequent experiment.

3.3 Effect of solvent to feed (S/F) ratio

S/F ratio is also important in extraction processes; to maximise extraction, solvent volume must be sufficient to immerse the entire sample and extract the phenolic. Insufficient solvent volume causes lower extraction yield because of non-uniform distribution of solvent into the plant matrix, so not all phenolics in CPH can be extracted, and yet the excessive solvent volume requires much energy and time to heat the solvent and extract the phenolic [14], and also high operating cost [9]. In this study, several S/F ratios (20:1, 30:1, 35:1, 40:1, and 50:1 v/w) were investigated to understand the influence of solvent volume on extraction yields. The results (Fig. 4) showed that, in general, the TPC yield of MAE and CSE increased with an increment in the S/F ratio from 20:1 to 50:1(v/w). Kaderides et al. [9] stated that a higher S/F ratio resulted in a larger concentration gradient between plant material and solvent. It also led to swelling of the plant material, enhancing the contact surface area between solvent and plant material, and yielded higher phenolic yield. However, a large solvent volume loading would need much energy and extraction time. Considering the consumption of less energy and observing the TPC of S/F ratio 40:1(v/w) had no high significant difference with 50:1(v/w), we proposed the S/F ratio 40:1(v/w) as the appropriate ratio to attain a high extraction yields.

Fig. 4 Effect of solvent to feed (S/F) ratio on TPC yields (CPH with particle size ≤ 38 -micron, 5 min extraction time, 50%(v/v) ethanol solvent, stirring rate 1200 rpm, temperature 60 °C for MAE and 70 °C for CSE), mean \pm S.D. (n=9, triplicate extraction and triplicate analysis)

3.4 Comparison of MAE and CSE

Microwaves heat volumetrically and selectively; volumetric heating enables the mixture to be heated instantaneously throughout, while selective heating allows the material to heat more rapidly, leading to potentially increased yields at shorter extraction times. This study, volumetric heating effect on MAE was neglected by designing the CSE experiment as MAE to have the same bulk heating profile (Fig. 1B). As a result, the extraction time for MAE and CSE were similar that was 5 min. Comparing the MAE at 60 °C and CSE at 70 °C for ethanol concentration and S/F ratio (Fig. 3A and Fig. 4), it is observed that TPC yields have no significant difference between both methods when

volumetric heating is neglected. However, MAE can produce a high TPC at lower extraction temperature, so energy requirements can be reduced. This may be caused by the selective heating effect on MAE process which leads to an increase in TPC yield. Fig. 3B showed that the presence of CPH in solvent increased the loss tangent of system which indicated that the CPH was selectively heated during microwave heating. Overall, high extraction yields were reached using 50%(v/v) ethanol (40/1 v/w) for 5 min at 60 °C for MAE (107.3±1.4 mg GAE/g dw) and 70 °C for CSE (105.4±0.9 mg GAE/g dw). Our result showed higher TPC compared to that of CPH extract from previous studies reported using CSE by Valadez-Carmona et al.[2] (18.9 mg GAE/ g dw), Yapo et al.[16] (68.9 mg GAE/ g dw), Vriesmann et al.[17] (98.0 mg GAE/g dw), Nguyen et al [18] (12.22 mg GAE/g dw), and MAE by Nguyen et al [10] (10.97 mg GAE/g dw).

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the comparison of MAE and CSE based on extraction parameters (extraction time and temperature, ethanol concentration, and S/F ratio) in terms of CPH valorisation. MAE was compared with CSE at the same bulk heating profile, stirrer speed, and solvent composition. The CSE experiments were designed by using a 120 °C ethylene glycol bath to achieve the same heating rate as MAE. It was found that by neglecting the volumetric heating, the maximum TPC for MAE and CSE can be achieved at the same time, which was 5 min. Meanwhile, the maximum conditions to reach maximum yield were using 50%ethanol at 60 °C for MAE with value 107.3±1.4 mg GAE/g dw and 60 °C for CSE with value 105.4±0.9 mg GAE/g dw. The extraction yield of TPC using MAE was similar to CSE at lower extraction temperature and 5% higher than CSE (102.6±0.9 mg GAE/g dw) at the same temperature (60 °C). It can be believed that this is due to the selective heating effect. This study suggests that MAE has potential to valorise CPH waste into valuable products through extraction of phenolic compounds. In future study, the activity of antioxidant and other valuable compounds such as anthocyanin content of CPH extract needs to be investigated.

References

- [1] R. Campos-Vega, K. H. Nieto-Figueroa, and B. D. Oomah, "Cocoa (Theobroma cacao L.) pod husk: Renewable source of bioactive compounds," *Trends Food Sci. Technol.*, vol. 81, pp. 172–184, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.tifs.2018.09.022.
- [2] L. Valadez-Carmona *et al.*, "Effects of microwaves, hot air and freeze-drying on the phenolic compounds, antioxidant capacity, enzyme activity and microstructure of cacao pod husks (Theobroma cacao L.)," *Innov. Food Sci. Emerg. Technol.*, vol. 41, no. February, pp. 378–386, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2017.04.012.
- [3] G. B. Teboukeu, F. Tonfack Djikeng, M. J. Klang, S. Houketchang Ndomou, M. S. L. Karuna, and H. M. Womeni, "Polyphenol antioxidants from cocoa pods: Extraction optimization, effect of the optimized extract, and storage time on the stability of palm olein during thermoxidation," *J. Food Process. Preserv.*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 1–11, 2018, doi: 10.1111/jfpp.13592.
- [4] O. R. Alara, N. H. Abdurahman, and C. I. Ukaegbu, "Extraction of phenolic compounds: A review," *Curr. Res. Food Sci.*, vol. 4, pp. 200–214, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.crfs.2021.03.011.
- [5] A. S. Caballero, J. M. Romero-Garcia, E. Castro, and C. A. Cardona, "Supercritical fluid extraction for enhancing polyphenolic compounds production from olive waste extracts Ashley S Caballero , a Juan M Romero-García , b Eulogio Castro b * and," *J Chem Technol Biotechnol*, vol. 95, pp. 356–362, 2020, doi: 10.1002/jctb.5907.
- [6] Z. Huma, V. Jayasena, S. M. Nasar-Abbas, M. Imran, and M. K. Khan, "Process optimization of polyphenol extraction from carob (Ceratonia siliqua) kibbles using microwave-assisted technique," *J. Food Process. Preserv.*, vol. 42, no. 2, 2018, doi: 10.1111/jfpp.13450.
- [7] S. Wang, A. H. Lin, Q. Han, and Q. Xu, "Evaluation of Direct Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction of Phenolic Compounds from Potato Peels," *Processes*, vol. 8, no. 12, p. 1665,

- 2020.
- [8] A. M. Galan *et al.*, “New insights into the role of selective and volumetric heating during microwave extraction: Investigation of the extraction of polyphenolic compounds from sea buckthorn leaves using microwave-assisted extraction and conventional solvent extraction,” *Chem. Eng. Process. - Process Intensif.*, vol. 116, pp. 29–39, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.cep.2017.03.006.
- [9] K. Kaderides, L. Papaikononou, M. Serafim, and A. M. Goula, “Microwave-assisted extraction of phenolics from pomegranate peels : Optimization , kinetics , and comparison with ultrasounds extraction,” *Chem. Eng. Process Intensif.*, vol. 137, no. January, pp. 1–11, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.cep.2019.01.006.
- [10] V. T. Nguyen, T. D. Pham, L. B. Vu, V. H. Nguyen, and N. Le Tran, “Microwave-assisted Extraction for Maximizing the Yield of Phenolic Compounds and Antioxidant Capacity from Cacao Pod Husk (Theobroma cacao L .) Abstract :,” *Curr. Nutr. Food Sci.*, pp. 1–4, 2020, doi: 10.2174/1573401316999200503032017.
- [11] A. C. Metaxas and R. J. Meredith, *Industrial Microwave Heating Industrial Microwave Heating*. The Institution of Engineering and Technology, London, United Kingdom, 1983.
- [12] M. Gharekhani, M. Ghorbani, and N. Rasoulnejad, “Microwave-Assisted Extraction of Phenolic and Flavonoid Compounds From Eucalyptus camaldulensis Dehn Leaves as Compared with Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction,” *Lat. Am. Appied Res.*, vol. 42, pp. 305–310, 2012.
- [13] I. Volf, I. Ignat, M. Neamtu, and V. I. Popa, “Thermal stability, antioxidant activity, and photo-oxidation of natural polyphenols,” *Chem. Pap.*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 121–129, 2014, doi: 10.2478/s11696-013-0417-6.
- [14] N. A. Ibrahim and M. A. A. Zaini, “Dielectric properties in microwave-assisted solvent extraction-Present trends and future outlook,” *Asia-Pacific J. Chem. Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 4, p. e2230, 2018, doi: 10.1002/apj.2230.
- [15] K. K. Chew, M. Z. Khoo, S. Y. Ng, Y. Y. Thoo, W. M. Wan Aida, and C. W. Ho, “Effect of ethanol concentration, extraction time and extraction temperature on the recovery of phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacity of Orthosiphon stamineus extracts,” *Int. Food Res. J.*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 1427–1435, 2011.
- [16] B. M. Yapo, V. Besson, B. B. Koukala, and K. L. Koffi, “Adding Value to Cacao Pod Husks as a Potential Antioxidant-Dietary Fiber Source,” *Am. J. Food Nutr.*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 38–46, 2013, doi: 10.12691/AJFN-1-3-4.
- [17] L. C. Vriesmann, R. D. de Mello Castanho Amboni, and C. L. De Oliveira Petkowicz, “Cacao pod husks (Theobroma cacao L.): Composition and hot-water-soluble pectins,” *Ind. Crops Prod.*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 1173–1181, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2011.04.004.
- [18] V. T. Nguyen, T. G. Tran, and N. Le Tran, “Phytochemical compound yield and antioxidant activity of cocoa pod husk (Theobroma cacao L.) as influenced by different dehydration conditions,” *Dry. Technol.*, vol. 0, no. 0, pp. 1–13, 2021, doi: 10.1080/07373937.2021.1913745.